

Ethnic level of intercultural relations

Marjona Mukhammadjonova

Student of UZSWLU

Anotation:

The national level of intercultural communication should be national unity. national unity is created on a mono-ethnic and multi-ethnic basis through common economic activity and state-political union. This is complemented by the formation of an appropriate culture.

Key words:

Cross-cultural, characters, ethnic, language, traditions, knowledge, building

Cross-cultural mutually of influence ethnic level local ethnos, ethno-linguistic, historical-ethnographic (general spiritual to culture according to), ethnic-confessional and another teams in the middle observed. Modern in ethnology ethnos is known one in the area historical formed, general cultural characteristics, self understanding and joint economic activity with separate standing people complex. Ethnic unity ethnicity organize doer people groups between kinship of connections existence to the idea is based on ethnic culture basically of ethnicity diary to his life concerned be, language, traditions, customs, customary law, values, knowledge, beliefs, people practical art types, tools, clothes, food, buildings, vehicles and others own into takes how culture like ethnic culture is also a continuum and update unit as manifestation will be of culture regeneration is endogenous (culture under the influence of external unaffected to the body comes) and exogenous (external from the side debt) to be it is possible while cross-cultural contact is the result.

MODERN EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES

Canada International Open Conference 2024

Ethnic level of cultures mutually under the influence of two trend sure manifestation will be Cultural of elements mutually assimilation to be done, one on the other hand, integration processes, mutually cultural to exchange and to get rich help gives another on the other hand, this ethnic self understand increase, ethnic to himself characteristic strengthening desire with together will come.

By itself, connections reinforcement, two tongue to know, mix marriages number increase and in others expressed ethnic level cross-cultural contact yet cultural the community to install take doesn't come Ethnicity culture system as his integration and stability provided only except "we" and "other Planets" from separation consists of ethnodifferential also performs the function. Har one ethnicity another ethnic of groups existence external event as acceptance does and him of life essence with cultural of appearance to each other dissimilarity separate with stands to him has been relationship interest or on the contrary, to reject take coming can of culture each how from the elements use as a result mutually or one bilaterally come in to go can but mutually divorce without losing cultural connections because of international culture elements they are formed based on different ethnic of groups connections done is increased. Such of culture to the elements the first in line international contact languages includes, they sure national to the compound have to be a must not to this tropical Africa peoples commercial and economic contact for which uses Swahili example by doing to bring can.

However, such culture heterogeneous of elements intensive mutually effect and agreement which provides maturity level have not of culture differentiate features hostility and violence for basis being service to do can, often disagreements and disputes come comes out Such of hostility too much except expression ethnocide to be can - dominant group by another ethnic of the group cultural traditions no to do With that together , weak group safe stay It is possible, but it is his ancestors culture loses or fundamentally changes . Of these all of them stable, high level, national level solidarity formation necessity about speaks.

Cross-cultural of communication national level national unity if so , it is

possible . National unity monoethnic and a lot nationality basically generality through to the body will come economic activity and state-political union . This is relevant culture formation with is filled . National culture is _ one nation , state representatives for common has been customs , norms , values and the rules is a set.

Nation state by organize done society cover received and society classification and social structure with separate standing because of national culture concept ethnic culture not to be possible has been social of groups subcultures cover takes. Ethnic cultures another the nation representatives row the national one too part to be can so, American national culture extremely different to him Irish, Italian, German, Chinese, Japanese, Mexican and another cultures enters Russian of culture diversity to say about can national of cultures most of them polyethnic, but ethnic of cultures different as , national cultures big in the regions living and kinship with depends didn't happen people unites.

Literature:

1. Cultures historical species (old and medium centuries) period change
2. Tsurikova cross-cultural of speech naturalness contact _ Voronezh : VSU, 2002
3. Gudkov and cross-cultural contact practice _ - M.: ITDGK "Gnosis", 2003

